

Rethinking Folic Acid

Fortification:

*A Pharmacogenomic
and
Policy-Based Reappraisal of
Neural Tube Defect Trends*

An Investigative Research Synthesis

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Alexandra Chambers
Independent researcher, Neurotopia CIC

ORCID: 0009-0002-6401-1908

Alexandra.chambers@ou.ac.uk

Abstract

This investigative research critically re-evaluates the widely accepted attribution of reduced neural tube defect (NTD) rates in Canada to folic acid fortification. Drawing on a parallel timeline analysis, the study identifies and contextualises several significant pharmacological and regulatory changes - specifically the concurrent withdrawal or restriction of known teratogenic anticonvulsants - that occurred during the implementation of fortification policy. The analysis integrates historical prescribing data, known teratogenic mechanisms, and the chronological overlap of drug market exits with declining NTD incidence. Evaluation reveals that these co-occurring variables represent substantial confounding factors. In addition, the paper incorporates a research synthesis on the biochemical limitations of synthetic folic acid, including the role of unmetabolised folic acid (UMFA), differential receptor binding, and genetic utilisation variance. The collated findings challenge the prevailing narrative that fortification was responsible for improved NTD outcomes and suggest an ongoing triple hit hypothesis; involving MTHFR susceptibility, anti-seizure medication (ASM) exposure, and hidden folate and B12 insufficiency as a plausible driver of paradoxical neural tube defect trends in the UK. This compilation highlights that a reassessment of causality is required in population-level nutrition policy to safeguard public health. Pharmacogenomic and nutritional profiling, including assessment of B12 and folate sufficiency, should be prioritised in women of reproductive age before the prescribing of anti-seizure medications. This analysis underscores the need for rigorous pharmacological context in public health modelling and offers an evidence-based call for transparency in attributing outcomes to broad scale interventions.

Introduction

The 2007 paper titled *Reduction in Neural-Tube Defects After Folic Acid Fortification in Canada* by De Wals et al.¹ overlooks major confounders in its methodology: the phased withdrawal of teratogenic anti-seizure medications (ASMs) such as paramethadione and trimethadione.²⁻³ Both in circulation since the 1940s and both discontinued by 1995, with reduced prescribing prior to the fact - a standard response due to known teratogenic risk.⁴ This reduction in foetal exposure would have resulted in falling neural tube defect (NTD) rates, independent of fortification. This paper presents a timeline of these pharmacological changes to demonstrate that these events were not only relevant, but critically unaccounted for.

This research synthesis also challenges the safety of ongoing folic acid fortification by examining key biochemical mechanisms, including the accumulation of unmetabolised folic acid (UMFA) and the variety of associated health indications. Through examining the dualistic masking of both folate and vitamin B12 insufficiency, anti-seizure medication (ASM) usage and the influence of MTHFR polymorphisms, a biologically plausible triple-hit model emerges. This hypothesis seeks to increase mechanistic understanding regarding the increased incidence of anencephaly in the UK. The importance of pharmacogenomics and an individualised approach is underscored for both clinical practice and the determination of national policy.

Omitted Pharmacological Confounders

- Sodium Valproate/ Depakene (valproic acid) / divalproex sodium (Epival) / Ratio-Valproic

The Independent Medicines and Medical Devices Safety Review (IMMDSR) 2020 sodium valproate timeline demonstrates prescribing changes that occur with increased awareness of risk, to *reduce incidence of NTDs*. These include coordinated restriction of teratogens via guideline changes, PIL (Patient Information leaflet) updates, and reduced prescribing to women protocol prior to additional anti-seizure drug withdrawals.⁴⁻⁵ Additionally, two long-standing anticonvulsants were withdrawn - paramethadione (Paradione)² and trimethadione (Tridione)³ - widely known for their teratogenicity, causing severe congenital malformations including neural tube defects.^{4,6-8}

1. Paramethadione: (Paradione):

Listed as discontinued by Abbvie (formerly Abbott); prescribing declined up to cessation in the mid-1990s and records show the final production batch was in 1989.² The FDA formally withdrew the new drug application (NDA) in 2004 once Abbott's original patent had ended.⁹

2. Trimethadione (Tridione):

Also listed as discontinued by Abbvie (formerly Abbott) by the FDA; marketing of this drug finally ceased in 1995,¹⁰ though the NDA has remained active for several years.³

Timeline of Pharmacological Confounders

To contextualize the decline in neural tube defects (NTDs), the following table on page 5 presents a parallel timeline of folic acid fortification efforts, alongside pharmaceutical events that contributed to the observed data outcomes.

Year	Fortification/ Trial Progress: De Wals et al., 2007 ¹	Pharmaceutical/ Prescribing Events	Expected Pharmaceutical Based Data Impact (Independent of Fortification)
1993–1997	Baseline data window (Pre – Fortification) ¹	Paramethadione and trimethadione usage already in decline. Prescribing restrictions underway in clinical practice. ^{2-4,10}	Baseline elevated due to decades of teratogenic drug exposures; restrictions ongoing; decline underway. ^{2-4,10}
1994–1995	Still baseline/ pre-fortification ¹	Trimethadione discontinued in 1995. ¹⁰ Paramethadione ceased by mid-1990s (final batch 1989). ²	NTD rates continue declining, reflects reduced prescribing and previous withdrawals. ²⁻⁴
1996–1998	Mandatory folic acid fortification introduced in Canada ¹	Simultaneous tightening of sodium valproate prescribing; regulators advising reduced use in women of childbearing potential. ⁴	Observed reductions align with pharmaceutical prescribing changes. ²⁻⁴
Late 1990s–2000s	Post fortification period in De Wals et al. dataset ¹	Further sodium valproate/ Depakene / divalproex/ Epival/ Ratio-valproic restrictions: guideline changes, PIL updates, reduced prescribing to women of childbearing potential. ⁴	Additional NTD decline sustained by prescribing changes, creating appearance of causal link with fortification. Correlation, not causation. ⁴
2007	De Wals et al. published, concluding that folic acid fortification is associated with a significant reduction in NTDs. ¹	Health Canada recall/discontinuation of Depakene® 500 mg and ratio-VALPROIC® 500 mg. ⁵	Decline presented as effect of folic acid fortification; data significantly influenced by major drug prescribing restrictions & consecutive withdrawals. ^{2-5,10}

Geographic Heterogeneity

The 2007 paper by De Wals et al. concluded that “food fortification with folic acid was associated with a significant reduction in neural-tube defects in Canada.

Furthermore, the risk reduction appeared greatest in regions in which the rates were highest before the fortification program was implemented”.¹ While attributed to fortification, this gradient is more consistent with regional variation in prescribing and withdrawal of teratogenic drugs.^{2-5,10} However, this explanation was not modelled or considered.

Biochemical Distinction

Scientific discourse frequently uses the terms ‘folate’ and ‘folic acid’ interchangeably, for example the Goossens et al, 2021 paper titled *Properties and Reactivity of the Folic Acid and Folate Photoproduct 6-Formylpterin*¹¹. Regardless, folate confers to naturally occurring reduced vitamers in food, whereas folic acid (pteroylmonoglutamic acid) is the fully oxidised synthetic form used in supplements and fortification.¹² Incidentally, 5-MTHF (natural folate) is relatively light-stable on its own, except in the presence of riboflavin, a strong photosensitizer.¹³ Riboflavin has also been added to fortified foods in the US - its degradation is greatly accelerated under ordinary UVA/visible light, leading to oxidative breakdown products. This undermines Goossens et al.’s 2021 blanket attribution of 6-formylpterin to ‘folate’ and exposes another fortification practice that significantly erodes nutritional value.

In 1988 Mason & Selhub demonstrated that folic acid can be highly absorbed intact via protein at the intestinal brush border,¹⁴ however, this does not ensure effective metabolic utilisation. The superior bioavailability of folic acid is a categorical error: it

is not absorption into the bloodstream that benefits, but the conversion into active folates. Dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR) is so limited that folic acid accumulates unmetabolised in circulation, paradoxically competing with natural folate.¹² This has many varied documented adverse effects, such as functional folate deficiency and subsequent downstream health problems.¹⁶⁻¹⁷ Therefore, the common metric assessed to justify fortification (serum folate levels) is misleading, since it reflects circulating synthetic folic acid rather than true metabolic utilization.

Population exposure: UMFA has been detected in umbilical cord blood, confirming placental transfer and foetal exposure¹⁵, and nearly all serum samples from US children, adolescents and adults,¹⁸ and fasting plasma.¹⁷ As one carbon metabolism underpins DNA methylation, this raises the possibility that intake constitutes an epigenetic risk factor, with potential long-term adverse effects.^{12,19-21} In their 2022 study, Zsigrai et al. also revealed that folic acid directly alters gene expression in colorectal cancer cells, demonstrating both epigenetic and oncogenic concerns.²³

Early-Onset Colorectal Cancer (EOCRC)

- US: Ages 20–29 saw annual CRC increases of 1.7-4.9% between 2004-2016.²⁴⁻²⁵
- England: Incidence in ages 20-29 rose from 0.8/100,000 in 1993 to 2.8/100,000 in 2014.²⁶

Pattern: Persistent increases across cohorts/geographies. Screening may account for increased awareness.²⁷ However, this does not explain the continued ongoing increase; a spike-then-plateau would be expected if detection were primary.

Implication: EOCRC trends are consistent with environmental exposure risk - synthetic folic acid being time-aligned and biologically plausible.

Prostate Cancer and Serum Folate

- Meta-analysis: In their 2014 study, Tio et al. confirmed high circulating folate is linked to prostate cancer; whilst confirming this was not through dietary folate,²⁸ and in 2009 Figueirodo et al. implicated folic acid specifically.²⁹
- UK data: Since the early 1990s, prostate cancer incidence in males has increased by 53% (2017-19) and is projected to rise by a further 15% by 2038-40, reaching around 85,100 new cases annually.³⁰
- US data projection: Approximately 313,780 new prostate cancer cases are expected in 2025, with incidence in younger men showing a rising trend in recent years.³¹

Implication: Elevated levels of serum folate - and particularly UMFA from fortification or supplements - offer a coherent biological mechanism for the observed rise in prostate cancer incidence.

International Data Variations

International implementation of folic acid fortification demonstrates a consistent pattern of erasing baseline clarity. In some countries, voluntary industry adoption was widespread years before mandates were enacted, effectively removing a clean pre-fortification reference point.³² Such structural variability makes fortification appear unfalsifiable, while obscuring the contribution of contemporaneous pharmacological withdrawals^{2-5,10} that align with observed declines in NTDs.

In the United Kingdom, flour fortification has been effectively in place for many years through voluntary measures, despite the absence of a legal mandate.³³ The 2000 Committee on Medical Aspects of Food and Nutrition Policy (COMA) report states that 80–90% of breakfast cereals and many breads were already fortified with folic acid by the late 1990's.

In November 2024 the UK government announced legislation requiring mandatory folic acid fortification of non-wholemeal wheat flour, due to take effect by the end of 2026.³⁴ The long-standing voluntary exposure complicates baseline interpretation and obscures any potential clean before-and-after data comparison.

Recent surveillance data further challenge the assumption that fortification has delivered continuing protective benefit. In England, neural tube defect (NTD) prevalence rose from 12.1 per 10,000 births (2010–2014) to 13.6 per 10,000 (2015–2019), with the increase driven largely by anencephaly.³⁵ Scotland presents a similar picture: overall NTD prevalence showed no significant decline between 2000 and 2021, while anencephaly rates increased significantly after 2013.³⁵⁻³⁶ The UK is established in this data by Broughan et al. as unfortified prior to 2021. However, as

stated, widespread voluntary folic acid fortification has been in place in the UK for decades. This means the population has already been exposed to folic acid without informed consent or genomic understanding. Framing this period as unfortified is inaccurate; and serves as a misrepresentation that shields both government and industry from accountability, and risks misattributing future changes in neural tube defect prevalence.

Folate & B12 Insufficiency

Low maternal vitamin B12 is a well-established independent risk factor for neural tube defects, particularly anencephaly, with women in the lowest quartile of B12 facing a two- to five-fold higher risk, irrespective of folate intake.³⁷⁻³⁸ B12 deficiency impairs one-carbon metabolism, elevates homocysteine, and disrupts DNA methylation required for neural tube closure.³⁹⁻⁴⁰

Importantly, long-term reliance on synthetic folic acid does not resolve these B12-dependent pathways and may exacerbate both functional folate and B12 deficiency by masking haematological symptoms.⁴¹⁻⁴² This mechanism offers a plausible explanation for why anencephaly rates have risen in certain fortified populations, suggesting that folic acid exposure may obscure - rather than prevent - underlying vulnerability.

MTHFR and Pharmacological Vulnerability

UMFA related harms disproportionately affect genetic subgroups with MTHFR C677T polymorphisms, such as autistic individuals.⁴³ The MTHFR C677T polymorphism, reduces the efficiency of folate metabolism and subsequently raises

homocysteine levels.⁴⁴ Those with other MTHFR variants that are also relatively common in the general population are also at risk.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁵

In summary, folic acid has been shown to disrupt gene expression²¹, interfere with methylation processes²², and impair immune surveillance mechanisms such as natural killer cell function.^{17,19} Excess serum folate from folic acid, particularly in the absence of sufficient vitamin B12, has been linked to neurological impairment, haematological abnormalities,⁴¹⁻⁴² and suboptimal cognitive outcomes.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁷

Unmetabolised folic acid is now detectable in the vast majority of serum samples in fortified populations,¹⁸ reinforcing concerns about chronic systemic exposure.

Epidemiological data show temporal associations between fortification policies and rising colorectal and prostate cancer rates²⁴⁻²⁶, with additional studies directly linking circulating unmetabolised (serum) folic acid specifically to increased prostate cancer risk.²⁸⁻²⁹

Epilepsy: An Additional Risk factor

Several meta-analyses show that people carrying the T allele have a higher chance of developing epilepsy, with the risk strongest in those who inherit two copies (TT genotype).⁴⁸⁻⁴⁹ These same variants also influence treatment outcomes; in patients with high homocysteine, the C677T polymorphism has been linked to poorer seizure control and reduced response to antiseizure medication.⁵⁰

Pharmacogenomic studies confirm that MTHFR and related polymorphisms contribute to variability in both drug effectiveness and side-effects.⁵¹⁻⁵² Mechanistic studies support this connection: individuals with MTHFR variants who take

antiseizure medications show greater depletion of folate and vitamin B12, alongside elevated homocysteine, which is itself a pro-convulsant metabolite.⁵³⁻⁵⁵ In rare but severe cases, complete MTHFR deficiency has been reported to cause familial epileptic encephalopathy.⁵⁶ This creates a paradox; the very demographics who are genetically more likely to develop epilepsy are also those most vulnerable to the metabolic side-effects of the drugs used to prevent seizures. In women of reproductive age, this dual vulnerability is especially critical: folate antagonism, high-dose synthetic folic acid, and unrecognised B12 insufficiency present an at-risk state. This can converge with impaired one-carbon metabolism, compounding both seizure-related risks and teratogenic risks such as neural tube defects.

Hispanic populations also carry a disproportionately high prevalence of the MTHFR C677T polymorphism, known to reduce enzyme activity and impair one-carbon metabolism.⁵⁷ Analysis of the 1000 Genomes Project estimated the allele frequency at approximately 47% among Hispanics, compared with 36% in Europeans, 30% in East Asians, 12% in South Asians, and 9% in Africans. In Mexican Mestizo populations, homozygosity for the TT genotype occurs in around 25% of individuals, and in certain Amerindian groups it reaches 57%.⁵⁸ This high genetic prevalence is biologically relevant, as reduced MTHFR function is a well-established risk factor for neural tube defects (NTDs) in the context of folate and B12 imbalance.³⁹⁻⁴⁰

Consistent with this genetic susceptibility, U.S. surveillance data from 1999–2011 show that Hispanic women had consistently higher prevalence of NTD-affected pregnancies compared to non-Hispanic whites and blacks.⁵⁹ During this period, spina bifida prevalence was 4.17 per 10,000 births among Hispanics, compared with 3.22 in non-Hispanic whites and 2.64 in non-Hispanic blacks.

The convergence of genetic, nutritional, and pharmacological evidence highlights a high-risk subgroup that has been overlooked in current policy. MTHFR polymorphisms are associated with both epilepsy susceptibility and impaired folate metabolism,⁴⁸⁻⁴⁹ while vitamin B12 deficiency is an independent and well-established risk factor for anencephaly.^{38,42}

Lamotrigine: A Missing link?

Lamotrigine (Lamictal), is termed a 'newer' generation anti-seizure medication, most frequently prescribed to women with epilepsy, particularly in the UK and much of Europe.⁶⁰ US biomarker studies of lamotrigine monotherapy, conducted after the introduction of folic acid fortification and routine periconceptional supplementation, have generally reported no major reductions in serum folate, or vitamin B12; nor consistent rises in homocysteine over ~32 weeks of follow-up.⁶¹ However, these apparently null findings are artefacts of the post-fortification environment: after the 1998 US mandate, median serum folate concentrations in women of reproductive age rose sharply and the prevalence of low folate fell to <1% by 1999–2000.⁶² Under these conditions, serum folate largely reflects UMFA rather than functional folate status, masking antagonistic effects.

In contrast, Huang et al. (2016) observed significant reductions in serum folate among Chinese patients treated with anti-seizure medications, including lamotrigine, where no national folic acid fortification policy was in place.⁶³ This divergence highlights how post-fortification serum folate assays in the U.S. may obscure lamotrigine-related folate depletion, inflating biomarker values through circulating unmetabolised folic acid (UMFA).

Recent pregnancy-focused studies further confirm this metabolic distortion: women with epilepsy using lamotrigine show lower concentrations of active folate metabolites than untreated women.⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶ While higher antiseizure drug levels are associated with greater UMFA, a reduced ratio of active MTHF to inactive folate, and evidence of increased folate catabolism. These findings indicate that lamotrigine's antagonism is hidden, not absent, and that the prevailing fortification environment produces misleading biomarker profiles with significant implications for risk assessment.

Together, these factors culminate into a biologically plausible triple hit - MTHFR variants, anti-seizure medication exposure (including lamotrigine), and concealed dual folate and B12 insufficiency. This could aid in explaining the recent paradoxical rise in neural tube defects reported in UK surveillance data. This pattern warrants further investigation, ideally through comparing the UK with regions where the ASM Levetiracetam is prescribed first-line over Lamotrigine.

The precautionary implication is clear: women of reproductive age should undergo pharmacogenomic and nutritional profiling before lamotrigine is prescribed, to minimise avoidable teratogenic risk.

Corporate Context

In 2001, Abbott Laboratories acquired Knoll Pharmaceuticals (the pharmaceutical arm of BASF) for \$6.9 billion.⁶⁷ BASF itself remains one of the world's major industrial producers of synthetic folic acid, while the Knoll lineage - now within AbbVie - also included folate-antagonist teratogenic anticonvulsants that are now

withdrawn in America. Though this may be controversial, the dynamic does reflect a problem–solution–profit cycle whereby the same industrial actors - or their corporate successors - are implicated in creating or exacerbating a public health risk and profiting from its proposed remedy.⁶⁸

Conclusion

Folic acid fortification was introduced as a preventative measure for NTDs, and the research strongly indicates that its implementation has catalysed severe downstream consequences across multiple health domains. This includes rising rates of early onset cancers, and potentially irreversible epigenetic damage that also disproportionately affect the most genetically vulnerable populations.

The 2007 study by De Wals et al. was technically correct in reporting a temporal decline in neural tube defects after the introduction of folic acid fortification in Canada. However, the paper has been highly influential; universally cited as causal evidence, underpinning justification for global fortification policy. Correlation must not be misinterpreted as causation; the observed decline in neural tube defects independently reflects the withdrawal and restriction of several teratogenic drugs. This reflects the broader problem–solution–profit cycle, in which continued interventions sustain dependence, and an ongoing requirement for further solutions. Furthermore, cessation of the cycle would elucidate previously obscured patterns of harm, both historical and ongoing - and the structural interests that have profited from them.

Various peer reviewed studies exist on the risk-benefit analyses of folic acid and fortification, and show conflicting results; the majority demonstrating the potential for significant harm to the population. Geographical NTD data has previously been stratified by siloed teratogenic drug exposure versus non exposure, making fortification appear to be the mechanism of beneficial change. However, that data reflects an underlying - and unaccounted for - global pharmacological shift.

Future policy and clinical practice must therefore prioritise public health by moving beyond fortification-based frameworks. Strategies should incorporate pharmacogenomic and nutritional profiling, with routine assessment of functional B12 and folate in women prescribed any anti-seizure medications, including newer generations such as lamotrigine. Without such measures, surveillance will continue to misinterpret biomarker signals and avoidable teratogenic outcomes will further increase.

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